

1 **Effectiveness of dual active ingredient insecticide-treated**
2 **nets in preventing malaria: a systematic review and meta-**
3 **analysis**
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17 **Abstract**

18 Malaria vectors have demonstrated resistance to pyrethroid-based insecticides used in insecticide-
19 treated nets, diminishing their effectiveness. This systematic review and meta-analysis investigated two
20 forms of dual active-ingredient (DAI) insecticide-treated nets (ITN(s)) for malaria prevention.

21 A comprehensive search was conducted on July 6th 2022. The databases searched included PubMed,
22 Embase, CINAHL, amongst others. Trials were eligible if they were conducted in a region with ongoing
23 malaria transmission. The first DAI ITN investigated were those that combined a pyrethroid with a non-
24 pyrethroid insecticides. The second DAI ITN investigated were that combined a pyrethroid with an
25 insect growth regulator. These interventions were compared against either a pyrethroid-only ITN, or
26 ITNs treated with pyrethroid and piperonyl-butoxide.

27 Assessment of risk of bias was conducted in duplicate using the Cochrane risk of bias 2 tool for cluster-
28 randomised trials. Summary data was extracted using a custom data-extraction instrument. This was
29 conducted by authors THB, JCS and SH. Malaria case incidence was the primary outcome and has been
30 meta-analysed, adverse events were narratively synthesised. The review protocol is registered on
31 PROSPERO (CRD42022333044).

32 From 9494 records, 48 reports were screened and 13 reports for three studies were included. These
33 studies contained data from 186 clusters and all reported a low risk of bias. Compared to pyrethroid-
34 only ITNs, clusters that received pyrethroid-non-pyrethroid DAI ITNs were associated with 305 fewer
35 cases per 1000-person years (from 380 fewer cases to 216 fewer cases) (IRR = 0.55, 95% CI: 0.44-0.68).
36 However, this trend was not observed in clusters that received pyrethroid-insect growth regulator ITNs
37 compared to pyrethroid-only ITNs (from 280 fewer cases to 135 more) (IRR = 0.90, 95% CI: 0.73-1.13).

38 Pyrethroid-non-pyrethroid DAI ITNs demonstrated consistent reductions in malaria case incidence and
39 other outcomes across multiple comparisons. Pyrethroid-non-pyrethroid DAI ITNs may present a novel
40 intervention for the control of malaria.

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Summary of Findings

Table 1: Evidence Profile: Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs compared to pyrethroid-only ITNs for prevention of malaria

Certainty assessment							Summary of findings				
Participants (studies) Follow-up	Risk of bias	Inconsistency	Indirectness	Imprecision	Publication bias	Overall certainty of evidence	Study event rates (%)		Relative effect (95% CI)	Anticipated absolute effects	
							With Pyrethroid-only nets	With Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid nets		Risk with Pyrethroid-only nets	Risk difference with Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid nets

Malaria Case Incidence (overall)

2000-person years (2 RCTs)	not serious	not serious	not serious	not serious	none	⊕⊕⊕⊕ High ^{a,b}	677.58 cases over 1000-person years (67.8%)	355.44 cases over 1000-person years (35.5%)	Incidence Rate Ratio 0.55 (0.44 to 0.68)^c	678 cases per 1,000-person years	305 fewer cases per 1,000-person years (from 380 fewer cases to 216 fewer cases)^d
Length of time observed: <1 month to 24 months											
Based on data from at least 61,183 participants (participant numbers unavailable in 1 study)											

Malaria Case Incidence (1-year post-intervention)

2000-person years (2 RCTs)	not serious	not serious	not serious	not serious	none	⊕⊕⊕⊕ High ^{e,f}	485.52 cases over 1000-person years (48.5%)	213.01 cases over 1000-person years (21.3%)	Incidence Rate Ratio 0.47 (0.35 to 0.63) ^g	486 cases per 1,000-person years	257 fewer cases per 1,000-person years (from 315 fewer cases to 180 fewer cases) ^d
Length of time observed: <1 month to 12 months											
Based on data from at least 61,183 participants (participant numbers unavailable in 1 study)											

Malaria Case Incidence (2-years post-intervention)

2000 (2 RCTs)	not serious	not serious	not serious	not serious	none	⊕⊕⊕⊕ High ^{g,h}	815.38 cases over 1000-person years (81.5%)	465.12 cases over 1000-person years (46.5%)	Incidence Rate Ratio 0.67 (0.61 to 0.75) ^g	815 cases per 1,000-person years	269 fewer cases per 1,000-person years (from 318 fewer cases to 204 fewer cases) ^c
Length of time observed: 12 months to 24 months											
Based on data from at least 61,183 participants (participant numbers unavailable in 1 study)											

Parasite Prevalence (6-months follow-up)

2249 (1 RCT)	not serious	not serious	not serious	not serious	none	⊕⊕⊕⊕ High	412/1471 (28%)	231/1475 (15.6%)	OR 0.47 (0.32 to 0.69) ⁱ	312 per 1,000	165 fewer per 1,000 (from 212 fewer to 97 fewer)
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Parasite Prevalence (12-months follow-up)

2473 (1 RCT)	not serious	not serious	not serious	not serious	none	⊕⊕⊕⊕ High	642/1227 (52.3%)	509/1246 (40.9%)	OR 0.47 (0.31 to 0.71) ⁱ	523 per 1,000	277 fewer per 1,000 (from 361 fewer to 152 fewer)
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Parasite Prevalence (18-months follow-up)

5445 (2 RCTs)	not serious	not serious	not serious	not serious	none	⊕⊕⊕⊕ High ^{i,k}	1218/2716 (44.8%)	923/2729 (33.8%)	OR 0.63 (0.49 to 0.80) ⁱ	448 per 1,000	166 fewer per 1,000 (from 228.48 fewer to 90 fewer)
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Parasite Prevalence (24-months follow-up)

2471 (1 RCT)	not serious	not serious	not serious	not serious	none	⊕⊕⊕⊕ High	549/1199 (45.8%)	326/1272 (25.6%)	OR 0.45 (0.30 to 0.68) ⁱ	458 per 1,000	252 fewer per 1,000 (from 321 fewer to 146 fewer)
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CI: confidence interval; RR: risk ratio

47 **Explanations**

48 a. ICEMAN effect modifier credibility assessments were conducted on this analysis for vector (*An. funestus* versus *An. gambiae sensu stricto* and *An. coluzzii*). Test for subgroup differences between subgroups was $p = 0.02$ (chance
49 a very likely explanation). ICEMAN credibility assessment determined very low credibility, very likely no effect modification. Of note the ICEMAN tool is not intended to rule out a true difference. As such, only the overall effect
50 is presented however uncertainty remains. Forest plot and ICEMAN assessment presented in supplementary files.

51 b. ICEMAN effect modifier credibility assessments were conducted on this analysis for setting (Rural versus Mixed). Test for subgroup differences between subgroups was $p = 0.057$ (chance a very likely explanation). ICEMAN
52 credibility assessment determined very low credibility, very likely no effect modification. Of note the ICEMAN tool is not intended to rule out a true difference. As such, only the overall effect is presented however uncertainty
53 remains. Forest plot and ICEMAN assessment presented in supplementary files.

54 **c. Adjusted Incidence Rate Ratio**

55 d. Absolute calculation performed manually using unadjusted data, as GRADEPro cannot calculate using IRR

56 e. ICEMAN effect modifier credibility assessments were conducted on this analysis for vector (*An. funestus* versus *An. gambiae sensu stricto* and *An. coluzzii*). Test for subgroup differences between subgroups was $p = 0.88$ (chance
57 a very likely explanation). ICEMAN credibility assessment determined very low credibility, very likely no effect modification. Of note the ICEMAN tool is not intended to rule out a true difference. As such, only the overall effect
58 is presented however uncertainty remains. Forest plot and ICEMAN assessment presented in supplementary files.

59 f. ICEMAN effect modifier credibility assessments were conducted on this analysis for setting (Rural versus Mixed). Test for subgroup differences between subgroups was $p = 0.88$ (chance a very likely explanation). ICEMAN
60 credibility assessment determined very low credibility, very likely no effect modification. Of note the ICEMAN tool is not intended to rule out a true difference. As such, only the overall effect is presented however uncertainty
61 remains. Forest plot and ICEMAN assessment presented in supplementary files.

62 g. ICEMAN effect modifier credibility assessments were conducted on this analysis for vector (*An. funestus* versus *An. gambiae sensu stricto* and *An. coluzzii*). Test for subgroup differences between subgroups was $p = 0.05$ (chance
63 a very likely explanation). ICEMAN credibility assessment determined very low credibility, very likely no effect modification. Of note the ICEMAN tool is not intended to rule out a true difference. As such, only the overall effect
64 is presented however uncertainty remains. Forest plot and ICEMAN assessment presented in supplementary files.

65 h. ICEMAN effect modifier credibility assessments were conducted on this analysis for setting (Rural versus Mixed). Test for subgroup differences between subgroups was $p = 0.05$ (chance a very likely explanation). ICEMAN
66 credibility assessment determined very low credibility, very likely no effect modification. Of note the ICEMAN tool is not intended to rule out a true difference. As such, only the overall effect is presented, however uncertainty
67 remains. Forest plot and ICEMAN assessment presented in supplementary files.

68 **i. Adjusted Odds Ratio**

69 j. ICEMAN effect modifier credibility assessments were conducted on this analysis for vector (*An. funestus* versus *An. gambiae sensu stricto* and *An. coluzzii*). Test for subgroup differences between subgroups was $p = 0.71$ (chance
70 a very likely explanation). ICEMAN credibility assessment determined very low credibility, very likely no effect modification. Of note the ICEMAN tool is not intended to rule out a true difference. As such, only the overall effect
71 is presented however uncertainty remains. Forest plot and ICEMAN assessment presented in supplementary files.

72 k. ICEMAN effect modifier credibility assessments were conducted on this analysis for setting (Rural versus Mixed). Test for subgroup differences between subgroups was $p = 0.71$ (chance a very likely explanation). ICEMAN
73 credibility assessment determined very low credibility, very likely no effect modification. Of note the ICEMAN tool is not intended to rule out a true difference. As such, only the overall effect is presented however uncertainty
74 remains. Forest plot and ICEMAN assessment presented in supplementary files.

Table 2. Evidence Profile: Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid nets compared to pyrethroid-PBO nets for prevention of malaria

Certainty assessment							Summary of findings				
Participants (studies) Follow-up	Risk of bias	Inconsistency	Indirectness	Imprecision	Publication bias	Overall certainty of evidence	Study event rates (%)		Relative effect (95% CI)	Anticipated absolute effects	
							With Pyrethroid-PBO nets	With Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid nets		Risk with Pyrethroid-PBO nets	Risk difference with Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid nets

Malaria Case Incidence (overall)

2000-person years (1 RCT) Length of time observed: <1 month to 24 months Based on data from at least 61,183 participants (participant numbers unavailable in 1 study)	serious ^a	not serious	not serious	not serious	none	 Moderate	333.16 cases over 1000-person years (33.3%)	227.34 cases over 1000-person years (22.7%)	Incidence Rate Ratio 0.68 (0.59 to 0.79)	333 cases per 1,000-person years	107 fewer cases per 1,000-person years (from 137 fewer cases to 70 fewer cases) ^b
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Malaria Case Incidence (1-year post-intervention)

2000-person years (1 RCT) Length of time observed: <1 month to 12 months Based on data from at least 61,183 participants (participant numbers unavailable in 1 study)	serious ^d	not serious	not serious	very serious ^c	none	⊕○○○ Very Low	133.49 cases over 1000-person years (13.3%)	130.84 cases over 1000-person years (13.1%)	Incidence Ratio (0.71 to 1.36)	Rate 0.98	133 cases per 1,000-person years	3 fewer cases per 1,000-person years (from 39 fewer cases to 48 more cases) ^b
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Malaria Case Incidence (2-years post-intervention)

2000-person years (1 RCT) Length of time observed: 12 months to 24 months Based on data from at least 61,183 participants (participant numbers unavailable in 1 study)	serious ^d	not serious	not serious	not serious	none	⊕⊕⊕○ Moderate	482.95 cases over 1000-person years (48.3%)	314.95 cases over 1000-person years (31.5%)	Incidence Ratio (0.55 to 0.77)	Rate 0.65	483 cases per 1,000-person years	155 fewer cases per 1,000-person years (from 198 fewer cases to 101 fewer cases) ^b
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Parasite Prevalence (12-months follow-up)

2197 (1 RCT)	serious ^d	not serious	not serious	serious ^d	none	 Low	206/1071 (19.2%)	176/1126 (15.6%)	OR 0.78 (0.62 to 0.97)	192 per 1,000	42 fewer per 1,000 (from 73 fewer to 6 fewer)
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Parasite Prevalence (18-months follow up)

2406 (1 RCT)	serious ^d	not serious	not serious	serious ^e	none	 Low	502/1160 (43.3%)	509/1246 (40.9%)	OR 0.91 (0.77 to 1.04)	433 per 1,000	39 fewer per 1,000 (from 100 fewer to 17 more)
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Parasite Prevalence (24-months follow-up)

2531 (1 RCT)	serious ^d	not serious	not serious	not serious	none	 Moderate	512/1259 (40.7%)	326/1272 (25.6%)	OR 0.50 (0.42 to 0.60)	407 per 1,000	203 fewer per 1,000 (from 236 fewer to 163 fewer)
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78 **CI:** confidence interval; **RR:** risk ratio

79 **Explanations**

80 a. Only unadjusted data was available for use for this comparison, and therefore there are serious issues with risk of bias.

81 b. Absolute calculation performed manually as GRADEPro cannot calculate using IRR.

82 c. Confidence intervals are very wide (39 fewer to 48 more) and may have crossed many important decision-making threshold (including line of no effect).

83 d. Confidence intervals are wide (73 fewer to 6 fewer) and may have crossed many important decision-making thresholds.

84 e. Confidence intervals are wide (from 100 fewer to 17 more) and may have crossed many important decision-making threshold (including line of no effect).

Table 3. Evidence Profile: Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid nets compared to pyrethroid-only nets for prevention of malaria

Certainty assessment							Summary of findings				
Participants (studies) Follow-up	Risk of bias	Inconsistency	Indirectness	Imprecision	Publication bias	Overall certainty of evidence	Study event rates (%)		Relative effect (95% CI)	Anticipated absolute effects	
							With Pyrethroid-only nets	With Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid nets		Risk with Pyrethroid-only nets	Risk difference with Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid nets

Malaria Case Incidence (overall)

2000-person years (3 RCTs) Length of time observed: 5 months to 24 months Based on data from at least 63,163 participants (participant numbers unavailable in 1 study)	not serious	not serious	not serious	very serious ^a	none	⊕⊕○○ Low ^{b,c,d}	1036.93 cases over 1000-person years (103.7%)	929.22 cases over 1000-person years (92.9%)	Incidence Rate Ratio 0.90 (0.73 to 1.13) ^e	1,037 cases per 1,000-person years	104 fewer cases per 1,000-person years (from 280 fewer cases to 135 more cases) ^f
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Malaria Case Incidence (1-year post-intervention)

2000-person years (2 RCTs) Length of time observed: <1 month to 12 months Based on data from at least 61,183 participants (participant numbers unavailable in 1 study)	not serious	not serious	not serious	not serious	none	⊕⊕⊕⊕ High ^{g,h}	485.52 cases over 1000-person years (48.6%)	392.74 cases over 1000-person years (39.3%)	Incidence Rate Ratio 0.66 (0.47 to 0.85) ^e	487 cases per 1,000-person years	166 fewer cases per 1,000-person years (from 258 fewer cases to 73 fewer cases) ^f
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Malaria Case Incidence (2-year post-intervention)

2000 (2 RCTs) Length of time observed: 12 months to 24 months Based on data from at least 61,183 participants (participant numbers unavailable in 1 study)	not serious	not serious ⁱ	not serious	very serious ^j	none	⊕⊕⊕○ Moderate ^{k,l}	815.39 cases over 1000-person years (81.5%)	715.84 cases over 1000-person years (71.6%)	Incidence Rate Ratio 0.94 (0.75 to 1.17) ^e	815 cases per 1,000-person years	49 fewer per 1,000 (from 204 fewer to 138 more) ^f
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Parasite Prevalence (6-months follow-up)

2934 (1 RCT)	not serious	not serious	not serious	serious ^m	none	⊕⊕⊕○ Moderate	412/1471 (28.0%)	394/1463 (26.9%)	OR 0.92 (0.63 to 1.34) ⁿ	280 per 1,000	22 fewer per 1,000 (from 104 fewer to 95 more)
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Parasite Prevalence (12-months follow-up)

2192 (1 RCT)	not serious	not serious	not serious	serious ^o	none	⊕⊕⊕○ Moderate	350/1123 (31.2%)	232/1069 (21.7%)	OR 0.69 (0.46 to 1.04) ⁿ	96 per 1,000	93 fewer per 1,000 (from 168 fewer to 12 more)
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Parasite Prevalence (18-months follow-up)

5337 (2 RCTs)	not serious	not serious	not serious	very serious ^p	none	⊕⊕○○ Low ^{q,r}	1218/2716 (44.8%)	1147/2631 (43.8%)	OR 0.97 (0.76 to 1.26) ⁿ	448 per 1,000	13 fewer per 1,000 (from 108 fewer to 116 more)
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Parasite Prevalence (24-months follow-up)

2457 (1 RCT)	not serious	not serious	not serious	serious ^s	none	⊕⊕⊕○ Moderate	549/1199 (45.8%)	472/1258 (37.5%)	OR 0.77 (0.54 to 1.16) ⁿ	458 per 1,000	105 fewer per 1,000 (from 192 fewer to 13 more)
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CI: confidence interval; RR: risk ratio

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89 **Explanations**

- 90 a. Confidence intervals are very wide (from 280 fewer to 135 more) and may have crossed many important decision-making threshold (including line of no effect).
- 91 b. ICEMAN effect modifier credibility assessments were conducted on this analysis for net type (Royal Guard versus Sumitomo Chemical). Test for subgroup differences between subgroups was $p = 0.89$ (chance a very likely
92 explanation). ICEMAN credibility assessment determined very low credibility, very likely no effect modification. Of note the ICEMAN tool is not intended to rule out a true difference. As such, only the overall effect is presented
93 however uncertainty remains. Forest plot and ICEMAN assessment presented in supplementary files.
- 94 c. ICEMAN effect modifier credibility assessments were conducted on this analysis for vector (*An. funestus* versus *An. gambiae sensu stricto* and *An. coluzzii*). Test for subgroup differences between subgroups was $p = 0.20$ (chance
95 a very likely explanation). ICEMAN credibility assessment determined very low credibility, very likely no effect modification. Of note the ICEMAN tool is not intended to rule out a true difference. As such, only the overall effect
96 is presented however uncertainty remains. Forest plot and ICEMAN assessment presented in supplementary files.
- 97 d. ICEMAN effect modifier credibility assessments were conducted on this analysis for setting (Rural versus Mixed). Test for subgroup differences between subgroups was $p = 0.57$ (chance a very likely explanation). ICEMAN
98 credibility assessment determined very low credibility, very likely no effect modification. Of note the ICEMAN tool is not intended to rule out a true difference. As such, only the overall effect is presented however uncertainty
99 remains. Forest plot and ICEMAN assessment presented in supplementary files.
- 100 e. Adjusted Incidence Rate Ratio
- 101 f. Absolute calculation performed manually as GRADEPro cannot calculate using IRR
- 102 g. ICEMAN effect modifier credibility assessments were conducted on this analysis for vector (*An. funestus* versus *An. gambiae sensu stricto* and *An. coluzzii*). Test for subgroup differences between subgroups was $p = 0.35$ (chance
103 a very likely explanation). ICEMAN credibility assessment determined low credibility, likely no effect modification. Of note the ICEMAN tool is not intended to rule out a true difference. As such, only the overall effect is presented
104 however uncertainty remains. Forest plot and ICEMAN assessment presented in supplementary files.
- 105 h. ICEMAN effect modifier credibility assessments were conducted on this analysis for setting (Rural versus Mixed). For each subgroup the IRR was: Rural = 0.79 (0.66, 0.95); Mixed = 0.83 (0.67, 1.03). Test for subgroup
106 differences between subgroups was $p = 0.94$ (chance a very likely explanation). ICEMAN credibility assessment determined very low credibility, very likely no effect modification. Of note the ICEMAN tool is not intended to rule
107 out a true difference. As such, only the overall effect is presented however uncertainty remains. Forest plot and ICEMAN assessment presented in supplementary files.
- 108 i. Borderline inconsistency, point estimate vary to some extent and I2 48%. However, not deemed serious enough to rate down.
- 109 j. Confidence intervals are very wide (from 204 fewer to 138 more) and may have crossed an important decision-making threshold (line of no effect).
- 110 k. ICEMAN effect modifier credibility assessments were conducted on this analysis for vector (*An. funestus* versus *An. gambiae sensu stricto* and *An. coluzzii*). Test for subgroup differences between subgroups was $p = 0.97$ (chance
111 a very likely explanation). ICEMAN credibility assessment determined very low credibility, very likely no effect modification. Of note the ICEMAN tool is not intended to rule out a true difference. As such, only the overall effect
112 is presented however uncertainty remains. Forest plot and ICEMAN assessment presented in supplementary files.
- 113 l. ICEMAN effect modifier credibility assessments were conducted on this analysis for setting (Rural versus Mixed). Test for subgroup differences between subgroups was $p = 0.71$ (chance a very likely explanation). ICEMAN
114 credibility assessment determined very low credibility, very likely no effect modification. Of note the ICEMAN tool is not intended to rule out a true difference. As such, only the overall effect is presented however uncertainty
115 remains. Forest plot and ICEMAN assessment presented in supplementary files.
- 116 m. Confidence intervals are wide (from 103 fewer to 95 more) and may have crossed many important decision-making thresholds (including line of no effect).
- 117 n. Adjusted Odds Ratio
- 118 o. Confidence intervals are wide (from 168 fewer to 12 more) and may have crossed many important decision-making thresholds (including line of no effect).
- 119 p. Confidence intervals are very wide (from 206 fewer to 72 more) and may have crossed many important decision-making thresholds (including line of no effect).

- 120 q. ICEMAN effect modifier credibility assessments were conducted on this analysis for vector (*An. funestus* versus *An. gambiae sensu stricto* and *An. coluzzii*). Test for subgroup differences between subgroups was $p = 0.50$ (chance
121 a very likely explanation). ICEMAN credibility assessment determined very low credibility, very likely no effect modification. Of note the ICEMAN tool is not intended to rule out a true difference. As such, only the overall effect
122 is presented however uncertainty remains. Forest plot and ICEMAN assessment presented in supplementary files.
- 123 r. ICEMAN effect modifier credibility assessments were conducted on this analysis for setting (Rural versus Mixed). Test for subgroup differences between subgroups was $p = 0.28$ (chance may not explain). ICEMAN credibility
124 assessment determined low credibility, likely no effect modification. Of note the ICEMAN tool is not intended to rule out a true difference. As such, only the overall effect is presented however uncertainty remains. Forest plot and
125 ICEMAN assessment presented in supplementary files.
- 126 s. Confidence intervals are wide (from 192 fewer to 13 more) and may have crossed many important decision-making thresholds (including line of no effect).

Table 4. Evidence Profile: Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid nets compared to pyrethroid-PBO nets for prevention of malaria

Certainty assessment							Summary of findings				
Participants (studies) Follow-up	Risk of bias	Inconsistency	Indirectness	Imprecision	Publication bias	Overall certainty of evidence	Study event rates (%)		Relative effect (95% CI)	Anticipated absolute effects	
							With Pyrethroid-PBO nets	With Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid nets		Risk with Pyrethroid-PBO nets	Risk difference with Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid nets

Malaria Case Incidence (overall)

2000-person years (1 RCT) Length of time observed: <1 month to 24 months Based on data from at least 61,183 participants (participant numbers unavailable in 1 study)	serious ^a	not serious	not serious	not serious	none	 Moderate	333.16 cases over 1000-person years (33.3%)	415.98 cases over 1000-person years (41.6%)	Incidence Rate Ratio 1.25 (1.10 to 1.41)	333 cases per 1,000-person years	83 more cases per 1,000-person years (from 33 more cases to 137 more cases) ^b
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Malaria Case Incidence (1-year post-intervention)

2000-person years (1 RCT)	serious ^a	not serious	not serious	not serious	none	⊕⊕⊕○ Moderate	130.84 cases over 1000-person years (13.1%)	266.33 cases over 1000-person years (26.6%)	Incidence Rate Ratio 2.04 (1.55 to 2.68)	131 cases per 1,000-person years	136 more cases per 1,000-person years (from 72 more cases to 220 more cases) ^b
Length of time observed: <1 month to 12 months											
Based on data from at least 61,183 participants (participant numbers unavailable in 1 study)											

Malaria Case Incidence (2-years post-intervention)

2000-person years (1 RCT)	serious ^a	not serious	not serious	serious ^c	none	⊕⊕○○ Low	482.95 cases over 1000-person years (48.3%)	530.86 cases over 1000-person years (53.1%)	Incidence Rate Ratio 1.10 (0.95 to 1.27)	483 cases per 1,000-person years	48 more cases per 1,000-person years (from 24 fewer cases to 130 more cases) ^b
Length of time observed: 12 months to 24 months											
Based on data from at least 61,183 participants (participant numbers unavailable in 1 study)											

Parasite Prevalence (12-months follow-up)

2140 (1 RCT)	serious ^a	not serious	not serious	serious ^d	none	 Low	206/1071 (19.2%)	232/1,069 (21.7%)	OR 1.16 (0.94 to 1.44)	192 per 1,000	31 more per 1,000 (from 11 fewer to 84 more)
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Parasite Prevalence (18-months follow-up))

2313 (1 RCT)	serious ^a	not serious	not serious	not serious	none	 Moderate	502/1160 (43.3%)	583/1,153 (50.6%)	OR 1.34 (1.14 to 1.58)	433 per 1,000	147 more per 1,000 (from 61 more to 251 more)
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Parasite Prevalence (24-months follow-up)

2517 (1 RCT)	serious ^a	not serious	not serious	serious ^e	none	 Low	512/1259 (40.7%)	472/1,258 (37.5%)	OR 0.88 (0.75 to 1.03)	407 per 1,000	49 fewer per 1,000 (from 102 fewer to 12 more)
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129 CI: confidence interval; OR: odds ratio; RR: risk ratio

130 Explanations

131 a. Only unadjusted data was available for use for this comparison, and therefore there are serious issues with risk of bias.

132 b. Absolute calculation performed manually as GRADEPro cannot calculate using IRR

133 c. Confidence intervals are very wide (from 24 fewer 130 more) and may have crossed many important decision-making thresholds (including line of no effect).

134 d. Confidence intervals are wide (from 11 fewer to 84 more) and may have crossed many important decision-making thresholds (including line of no effect).

135 e. Confidence intervals are wide (from 102 fewer to 12 more) and may have crossed many important decision-making thresholds (including line of no effect).

136

137 Introduction

138 Malaria is an infectious, parasitic disease transmitted through the bite of infected female *Anopheles* mosquitoes.¹
139 Malaria is caused by the *Plasmodium* parasite, with *P. falciparum* and *P. vivax* species being the most virulent
140 and widespread for human hosts.¹ Malaria presents a significant burden to global public health, with an estimated
141 247 million malaria cases in 2021² Substantial progress has been made since 2000 in reducing global malaria
142 cases from 80 cases per 1000 persons at risk to 57 per 1000 persons at risk in 2019. However, there was recently
143 an increase in this metric to 59 per 1000 persons at risk observed in 2020.² The most successful malaria
144 prevention strategies have often included the distribution of insecticide-treated nets (ITN) distribution of ITNs
145 is estimated to have contributed an estimated 68% to the reduction of the malaria burden.²

146 The WHO recommends that ITNs treated with a pyrethroid-based insecticide be used for large-scale
147 deployment.³ These ITNs are prequalified by WHO and are treated with pyrethroid at the time of manufacture
148 and have demonstrated public health value whilst meeting safety standards. However, recent findings have
149 demonstrated that both *Anopheles gambiae* (s.s.) and *An. funestus* (s.s.), the most prevalent malaria vectors,
150 have developed widespread resistance to these pyrethroid insecticides.^{6,7} This may compromise the long-term
151 effectiveness of these ITNs.¹ In response to the spread of pyrethroid resistance, the WHO has stated that new
152 types of ITNs should be developed to combat insecticide-resistant vectors.³ WHO has identified two additional
153 classes of ITNs, those designed to kill host-seeking insecticide-resistant mosquitoes and those designed to
154 sterilize and/or reduce their fecundity.

155 The former of these additional ITN classes, includes ITNs designed to kill resistant mosquitoes and consist of
156 combinations of pyrethroid insecticides and other active ingredients. Belonging to this class includes ITNs
157 treated with both a pyrethroid and piperonyl butoxide (PBO).¹ PBO is a synergist that acts to inhibit the
158 metabolic enzymes of the mosquito that work to detoxify (and therefore reduce effectiveness of) insecticides.
159 The benefits to public health of these pyrethroid-PBO ITNs have been demonstrated, resulting in the WHO
160 conditionally recommending that these nets be used, particularly in areas where pyrethroid-resistant mosquitoes
161 are present.¹ This class also provisionally includes ITNs that combine pyrethroids with other non-pyrethroid
162 active ingredients (henceforth referred to as dual active ingredient nets, DAI). Studies on one DAI ITN, that
163 combines alpha-cypermethrin (pyrethroid) and the pyrrole chlorfenapyr have recently demonstrated both
164 entomological and epidemiological benefit.^{4,5} Finally, the third class of ITNs include those that have been
165 designed to sterilize and/or reduce the fecundity of host-seeking insecticide-resistant mosquitoes. This class
166 provisionally includes DAI ITNs treated with a pyrethroid insecticide and an insect growth regulator such as
167 pyriproxyfen. Pyriproxyfen is an insecticide that interferes with the reproduction and development of female
168 mosquitoes, effectively sterilising them.⁵

169 The value to public health of DAI ITNs treated with both pyrethroids and insect growth regulators has not been
170 established until recently. DAI ITNs may provide a solution to address vector pyrethroid resistance and may
171 prove to have utility in future malaria control programmes. There is an urgent need to systematically review
172 the evidence on the effectiveness of DAI ITNs as tools for the control and prevention of malaria.

173 This systematic review is specifically interested in two interventions. These interventions will be considered as
174 separate review questions. The first intervention includes DAI ITNs treated with a pyrethroid and non-
175 pyrethroid insecticide. The second intervention includes DAI ITNs treated with a pyrethroid and an insect
176 growth regulator. The main objective of this review is to assess the benefits (on malaria transmission or burden)
177 and harms (adverse effects and unintended consequences) of insecticidal nets treated with a pyrethroid and a
178 second active ingredient (either non-pyrethroid insecticide or insect growth regulator). Two review questions
179 were formulated for this review, these questions are as follows:

- 180 1. In areas with ongoing malaria transmission, should long last insecticidal nets treated with a pyrethroid
181 and non-pyrethroid insecticide versus either nets treated with pyrethroid insecticide alone or with

182 pyrethroid insecticide in combination with Piperonyl butoxide (PBO) be used to prevent malaria in
183 adults and children?

184 2. In areas with ongoing malaria transmission, should long lasting insecticidal nets treated with a
185 pyrethroid and an insect growth regulator versus either nets treated with pyrethroid insecticide alone or
186 with pyrethroid insecticide in combination with PBO be used to prevent malaria in adults and children?

187 **Methods**

188 The methodology of this systematic review and meta-analyses is based on methods guidance from the Cochrane
189 Handbook,⁸ JBI Manual for Evidence Synthesis,⁹ and the GRADE Working Group.¹⁰ It has been reported in
190 line with PRISMA 2020. The protocol was registered a priori on PROSPERO (registration number
191 CRD42022333044) and has been published in F1000Research.¹¹

192 **Eligibility Criteria**

193 **Participants**

194 Studies conducted in adults and children who are residents of a region with ongoing malaria transmission and
195 have been provided with an insecticide-treated net were eligible for this review.

196 **Interventions**

197 The interventions of interest are dual active ingredient (DAI) insecticide-treated nets (ITNs). DAI ITNs are
198 eligible where they have been treated with a pyrethroid and non-pyrethroid insecticide (review question 1) or
199 with a pyrethroid and an insect growth regulator (review question 2). The level of ITN distribution (per
200 household or per individual) did not impact the eligibility of studies for inclusion in the review.

201 **Background interventions**

202 Studies conducted where background interventions were present were included if these background
203 interventions were balanced between intervention and control arms.

204 **Comparators**

205 This systematic review considered studies that have compared the interventions of interest against nets treated
206 with pyrethroid insecticide alone or with pyrethroid insecticide in combination with PBO. The same
207 comparator(s) was used for both review questions specified above.

208 **Outcomes**

209 The following outcomes were considered for inclusion and are grouped into epidemiological outcomes,
210 entomological outcomes, unintended benefits, and harms/ unintended consequences.

211 **Epidemiological**

- 212 • Malaria case incidence rate – Defined as [malaria] symptoms plus [malaria] parasitaemia, over a
213 population at risk or person-time. Detected either through passive or active surveillance.
- 214 • Malaria infection incidence – Defined as parasitaemia with or without symptoms, over a population at
215 risk or person-time. Detected through passive or active surveillance.
- 216 • Incidence of severe disease – Defined as hospitalisation with parasitaemia, over a population at risk or
217 person-time.
- 218 • Parasite prevalence – Parasitaemia with or without symptoms, over the population at risk for the
219 specified duration. Detected through cross-sectional surveys.
- 220 • All-cause mortality – Number of deaths over the population at risk or person-time.
- 221 • Malaria mortality – Number of deaths attributed to malaria over the population at risk or person-time.
- 222 • Prevalence of anaemia – Defined by study thresholds of anaemia.

223 **Entomological**

224 Studies containing data on entomological outcomes were only included in this review where data for
225 epidemiological outcomes were also reported. These outcomes were only listed during data extraction and have
226 not formed the basis of any outcome reporting.

- 227 • Entomological inoculation rate (EIR) – Defined as the number of infective bites received per person
228 per unit of time.
- 229 • Sporozoite rate – Percentage of female *Anopheles* mosquitoes with sporozoites in the salivary glands.
- 230 • Anopheline density – Number of female anopheline mosquitoes in relation to the number of specified
231 shelters or hosts or to a given period sampled, specifying the methods of collection.
- 232 • Biting rate – Average number of mosquito bites received by a host in a unit of time, specified according
233 to the host and mosquito species.
- 234 • Mortality of adult female *Anopheles* – Defined as the mosquito being knocked down, immobile or
235 unable to stand or take off for 24 hours after exposure to a discriminating concentration of an insecticide
236 (or as reported in the primary evidence).

237 **Contextual factors**

238 Studies containing data on contextual factors were only included in this review where epidemiological outcomes
239 were also considered by the primary study.

- 240 • Values and preferences – The values and preferences of the individuals and populations receiving the
241 intervention.
- 242 • Acceptability – Extent to which those receiving the intervention consider the intervention to be
243 appropriate, based on anticipated or experienced cognitive and emotional responses to the intervention.
244 Includes willingness to participate in the intervention.
- 245 • Health equity – Extent to which the intervention benefits all populations and the potential to
246 discriminate based on sex, age, ethnicity, culture, language, sexual orientation or gender identity,
247 disability status, education, socioeconomic status, residence, or any other characteristic.
- 248 • Financial and economic considerations – Costs, resource use, overall economic impact, cost-benefit,
249 cost effectiveness.
- 250 • Feasibility considerations – legal barriers to implementation, programmatic considerations, timeliness
251 (the ability to reach all targeted households/household members in a timely manner) etc.

252 **Unintended benefits**

- 253 • Epidemiological impact on other vector-borne diseases

254 **Harms and/or unintended consequences of interventions**

- 255 • Adverse effects known to be associated with insecticides, including skin irritation, irritation of upper
256 airways, nausea, and headache.
- 257 • Human behaviour changes e.g., change in sleeping location.
- 258 • Any influence on neighbouring houses e.g., increased vector abundance/biting in houses without nets
- 259 • Environmental impacts such as biodiversity and ecosystem changes.
- 260 • Entomological impacts e.g., mosquito behaviour changes such as changes in outdoor biting rate, biting
261 times, feeding preference, development of insecticide resistance, change in vector composition.

262 **Setting**

263 Studies conducted in countries with ongoing malaria transmission were considered for this review. The presence
264 of other background interventions did not impact on study eligibility if they were present in both arms equally.
265 Studies where additional malaria interventions are considered standard of care were included if interventions
266 (both malaria and non-malaria) were balanced between intervention and control arms.

267 **Study design**

268 Only cluster randomised and non-randomised cluster-controlled studies that included more than one cluster per
269 arm were considered for this review. Non-randomised controlled study designs were only considered for
270 inclusion when there was a comparison/control group present. This could include historical controls. There were
271 no exclusion rules based on any buffer period (i.e., when participants act as their own controls) or length of
272 intervention or timing of measurement of outcomes. All observational studies and modelling studies were
273 excluded.

274 Studies were not excluded based on language or publication status (i.e., published, unpublished, in press, in
275 progress, pre-print). There were no date limitations. For studies published in languages other than English,
276 Google Translate was to be used to determine whether the study meets inclusion criteria based on its title and
277 abstract. Where studies were published in a language other than English and met the inclusion criteria, Google
278 Translate translations were to be reviewed by a person fluent in that language.

279 **Search strategy**

280 The literature search methods have been conducted in line with guidance from JBI⁹ and Cochrane.⁸ The search
281 strategy aimed to locate both published and unpublished studies and was developed with the input of a medical
282 librarian.

283 An initial limited search of PubMed via NCBI was undertaken to identify relevant articles on this topic. The
284 terminology contained in the titles and abstracts of relevant articles, including related subject headings, were
285 used to develop a full search strategy for malaria and insecticidal nets. The search strategy, including all
286 identified keywords and subject headings, was adapted for each included database and/or information source,
287 by using Polyglot¹² and with the aid of a medical librarian. No limits or filters were applied to the searches. The
288 search strategies for each database were then peer-reviewed using the Peer Review of Electronic Search
289 Strategies Guideline Statement.¹³ The full search strategy for major databases is available in S1.

290 The databases searched included Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials (CENTRAL), published in The
291 Cochrane Library (Wiley) and including the Cochrane Infectious Diseases Group Specialized Register; PubMed
292 (NCBI); Embase (Ovid); CINAHL with Full Text (EBSCO), US National Institutes of Health Ongoing Trials
293 Register (www.ClinicalTrials.gov/); ISRCTN registry (www.isrctn.com/); The WHO's International Clinical
294 Trials Registry Platform (WHO ICTRP (www.who.int.ictrp)). Additionally, experts in the field and relevant
295 organisations were asked whether they know of any studies (completed or ongoing) that are relevant to this
296 review topic. The searches were run on June 7, 2022.

297 **Study selection and screening**

298 Following the search, all identified citations were collated and uploaded into EndNote (Clarivate, Philadelphia,
299 United States). Duplicates were removed using the Deduplicator.¹⁴ The studies were then imported into
300 Covidence (Veritas Health Innovation, Melbourne, Australia) where additional duplicates were identified and
301 removed. Within Covidence, the studies were screened on their titles and abstracts by two independent reviewers
302 (THB and SH) for assessment against the eligibility criteria for the review. Potentially relevant studies were
303 retrieved in full. The full text of selected citations was then assessed in detail against the eligibility criteria by
304 the same two independent reviewers. Studies that were excluded at full text screening as they did not meet the
305 eligibility criteria have been recorded and the reasons for their exclusion reported (S2). Any disagreements
306 between the two reviewers at each stage of the selection process were resolved through discussion.

307 **Data extraction**

308 Data was extracted from papers included in the review by three independent reviewers (THB, SH, JCS*) using
309 a tailored data extraction tool developed by the reviewers (S3). Any disagreements between the reviewers were

310 resolved through discussion. The authors of one study protocol¹⁵ were contacted directly for their data as the
311 results of their work had not yet been published (discussed in detail in the results).

312 **Assessment of risk of bias**

313 Three review authors (THB, SH, JCS*) assessed the risk of bias for each study using the Cochrane Risk of Bias
314 2 tool for cluster-randomised trials.¹⁶ The domains of bias considered in this tool include bias arising from the
315 randomisation process, bias arising from the timing of identification or recruitment of participants, bias due to
316 deviations from the intended interventions, bias due to missing outcome data, bias in measurement of the
317 outcome and bias in selection of the reported result. All risk of bias assessment was undertaken at the result
318 level. Any disagreements between the reviewers in assessing the risk of bias were resolved through discussion.

319 **Data synthesis and meta-analysis**

320 Where possible, epidemiological outcomes were pooled using pair-wise meta-analysis in Review Manager 5
321 (RevMan5). Results have been pooled when data for the same outcome has been reported between studies and
322 according to the active-ingredient composition of the DAI ITN intervention and of the pyrethroid-only ITN or
323 pyrethroid-PBO ITN comparators. Data were also pooled at time-points measured in the contributing studies
324 (6-months, 12-months, 18-months, 24-months post intervention). As some studies provided data for up to 18-
325 months post-intervention and some provided data for up to 24-months post-intervention, these outcome results
326 have been combined under the classification of ‘furthest possible follow-up’. Also included in this classification
327 is data derived from stepped-wedge trials. Where only one study had contributed data to a particular outcome,
328 a forest plot was presented for illustrative purposes. A narrative description of the results has been presented
329 alongside the meta-analysis. Where outcome data between studies cannot be pooled together in a meta-analysis,
330 a narrative synthesis has been presented.

331 For dichotomous data, effect sizes have been presented as **odds ratios**. These results have been presented with
332 their 95% confidence intervals (CIs). Where incidence rates were reported, incidence rate ratios have been
333 reported with their 95% CIs in the meta-analysis. When three or more studies contribute to a meta-analysis, a
334 random effects model has been used. A fixed effect model was used when there are only two studies contributing
335 to a meta-analysis. Cost data and data related to contextual factors have been narratively synthesised.
336 Entomological outcomes listed in the included studies have been reported in S3.

337 **Assessment of heterogeneity and publication bias**

338 Heterogeneity (both clinical and methodological) was first assessed by comparing the included studies against
339 each other in terms of the eligibility criteria specified above. Statistical heterogeneity was assessed through
340 visual inspection of the forest plot and by the Cochran’s Q (P value 0.05), and I² statistic. Interpretation of the
341 I² statistic was according to the guidance in the Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions⁸
342 and occurred as follows:

- 343 • 0% to 40%: heterogeneity might not be important;
- 344 • 30% to 60%: may represent moderate heterogeneity;
- 345 • 50% to 90%: may represent substantial heterogeneity; or
- 346 • 75% to 100%: considerable heterogeneity.

347 The typical statistical tests of publication bias were not appropriate^{17,18} as fewer than 10 studies were included
348 in all meta-analyses. Efforts were made to reduce the impact of publication bias in this review by seeking both
349 published and unpublished literature using the comprehensive search strategy discussed above and provided in
350 S1.

351 **Subgroup and sensitivity analysis**

352 Where the data was available, several potential effect modifiers were assessed through subgroup analyses. These
353 included:

- 354 • Insecticides used for both active ingredients and manufacturer.
- 355 • Malaria vector species.
- 356 • Setting (Urbanicity, classed as rural/ urban/ peri-urban).

357 Subgroups were assessed on their credibility of being a genuine effect modifier using the Instrument for
358 assessing the Credibility of Effect Modification (ICEMAN).¹⁹ This is a tool that reviewers can use based on
359 answering a series of questions that address specific criteria that can be used to evaluate whether an effect
360 modification is likely.¹⁹ ICEMAN credibility assessment statements are expressed as very low (very likely no
361 effect modification), low (likely no effect modification), moderate (likely effect modification), and high (very
362 likely effect modification).

363 **GRADE**

364 The GRADE approach¹⁰ for grading the certainty of evidence was followed. GRADE Evidence Profiles were
365 created using “GRADEpro GDT” for each comparison considered. The evidence profiles have presented the
366 following information for each outcome: absolute risks for the treatment and control, estimates of relative risk,
367 and a rating of the certainty of the evidence based. As all evidence has been derived from RCTs, the certainty
368 of evidence has started as high and has been downgraded appropriately. All instances of downgrading have been
369 documented in the footnotes in the summary of findings tables (Tables 1-4). The following outcomes have been
370 presented in the summary of findings tables (where applicable):

- 371 • Malaria case incidence rate (overall)
- 372 • Malaria case incidence rate (1-year post intervention)
- 373 • Malaria case incidence rate (2-years post intervention)
- 374 • Parasite prevalence (6-months follow-up)
- 375 • Parasite prevalence (12-months follow-up)
- 376 • Parasite prevalence (18-months follow-up)
- 377 • Parasite prevalence (24-months follow-up)

378 **Results**

379 **Results of the search**

380 There were 8998 citation records identified in the initial database search (i.e., PubMed, Embase, CINAHL,
381 Cochrane Library) and 496 citation records were identified from the trial registries (ClinicalTrials.gov, WHO
382 ICTRP, ISRCTN), for a total of 9494 citation records. Of these, a total of 3694 records were removed (3662
383 records were identified and removed via the Deduplicator¹⁴ and a further 32 records were identified and removed
384 via Covidence). This left 5800 unique citation records to be screened. Two citation records were identified
385 through direct correspondence with the authors (described below) and through manual searching through the
386 ClinicalTrials.gov trial registry. The former of these records was an ongoing trial (NCT04566510) which has
387 been noted for future reviews on this topic but has not contributed to any of the analysis of this report.

388 The records were screened by title and abstract and 5752 citations were excluded for not meeting the inclusion
389 criteria. This left 48 records in which the reports were sought and were screened at the full-text level. There
390 were 36 reports that were excluded for not meeting the inclusion criteria. Of these 36, 21 reports were excluded
391 for having an ineligible study design, eight reports were excluded for having ineligible outcomes and seven
392 reports were excluded for having ineligible interventions.

393 The 12 remaining reports were then merged at the study level, leaving three studies (12 reports) to be
394 included in the review. The report that was identified through direct correspondence with the authors
395 was an ongoing study that had been accepted for publication but was still in production (as of writing,
396 this study has been published by the Lancet). This study has been merged with the reports of the protocol
397 that were identified during the search and screening procedures. Therefore, the final totals were three
398 studies included in this review which have been reported in 12 reports identified through the search and

399 one report identified via direct correspondence with the study authors. The breakdown of reports to
400 studies is presented in Table 5.

401 **Table 5: Breakdown of reports to studies included in the systematic review**

Study Citation	Number of Reports
Accrombessi, Cook ^{15,20}	3 2 identified through screening 1 identified through direct author correspondence with authors
Mosha, Kulkarni ⁴	3
Tiono, Ouédraogo ²¹	7

402 The PRISMA flow diagram of this screening process is presented below (Fig 1).

403 **Fig 1. PRISMA Flow Diagram.** From: Page MJ, McKenzie JE, Bossuyt PM, Boutron I, Hoffmann TC, Mulrow
404 CD, et al. The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ*
405 2021;372:n71. doi: 10.1136/bmj.n71. For more information, visit: <http://www.prisma-statement.org/>

406 **Characteristics of the included studies**

407 **Study designs and time periods**

408 This review has included three studies,^{4,20,21} one of which was a trial¹⁵ that was only recently accepted for
409 publication²⁰ following peer-review. All the included studies were cluster-randomised control trials, with the
410 study from Tiono, Ouédraogo²¹ employing a stepped-wedge design for intervention implementation. The years
411 during which the trials took place were between 2014-2015,²¹ 2018-2020,⁴ and 2020-2022.²⁰

412 **Population, setting and vector characteristics**

413 The sample size ranged from approximately 4,000 households²⁰ to 39,307 households.⁴ The number of
414 participants for each study ranged from 1,980²¹ to 61,183.⁴ Studies included both adults and children in their
415 design, however children were prioritised in the measurement of the outcomes and population demographics
416 (data from adults included in select outcomes, detailed below). Accrombessi, Cook²⁰ reported data for adults
417 and children (collected from cross-sectional studies) and only children (active-case detection, details below)
418 between the ages of 6 months to 9 years old who did not have severe illnesses and resided in the study villages
419 at the time of the intervention. Mosha, Kulkarni⁴ included households with at least one child of appropriate age
420 (between six months to ten years old) who permanently lived in households recruited through a census. Adults
421 were also considered in the data from cross-sectional surveys (details below). Tiono, Ouédraogo²¹ (2018)
422 included children selected randomly from a census, who were between the ages of 6 months to 5 years old. The
423 percentage of female to male children was balanced for all included studies at 48%,²⁰ 51.7%⁴ and 49%.²¹

424 The countries involved in this review included Benin,²⁰ Burkina Faso²¹ and Tanzania⁴ with the trials in Burkina
425 Faso²¹ and Tanzania⁴ both being conducted in a setting of mixed urbanicity (mix of rural and peri-urban). The
426 study conducted in Benin was conducted in a rural setting.²⁰ Transmission intensity of malaria followed the
427 rainy season in each location, which ranged from April-July and October-November (Benin),²⁰ May-October
428 (Burkina-Faso)²¹ and October-July (Tanzania).⁴ The species of parasite for each trial was *Plasmodium*
429 *falciparum*, and every setting was considered to have a high level of transmission (*P. falciparum* prevalence of
430 $\geq 35\%$) according to the schema in the WHO: *a framework for malaria elimination*.²² The main vectors of
431 interest for the trials of Accrombessi, Cook²⁰ and Tiono, Ouédraogo²¹ included both *Anopheles coluzzi* and *An.*
432 *gambiae sensu stricto*. While the main vector considered by Mosha, Kulkarni⁴ was *An. funestus*.

433 **Interventions and Comparisons**

434 All studies implemented the intervention at the household level (e.g. distributed nets according to number of
435 people residing in each household), and every study reported to have achieved a high level of coverage.²³
436 Accrombessi, Cook²⁰ assessed coverage as household access, and reported that one net was provided per every
437 two people. Mosha, Kulkarni⁴ and Tiono, Ouédraogo²¹ assessed coverage as population access and reported a
438 baseline intervention coverage of 62.2% and 95%, respectively.

439 Accrombessi, Cook ²⁰ explored two interventions against a common comparator. The first intervention was the
440 chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITN “Interceptor G2®”. This ITN was made of polyester netting (100 deniers)
441 **impregnated** with a wash-resistant formulation of 200 mg/m² chlorfenapyr (a pyrole) and 100 mg/m² alpha-
442 cypermethrin (a pyrethroid). The second intervention was the pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITN “Royal Guard®”.
443 This ITN was made of polyethylene (120 deniers) incorporating 225 mg/m² pyriproxyfen (an insect growth
444 regulator) and 261 mg/m² alpha-cypermethrin. **Both interventions were compared against a control pyrethroid-
445 only ITN treated** with alpha-cypermethrin at a target dose of 200 mg/m² of polyester fabric (100 deniers).

446 Mosha, Kulkarni ⁴ also investigated two interventions. The first intervention was the “Interceptor G2®” (same
447 specifications as above) and the second was the “Royal Guard®” (same specifications as above). These
448 interventions were compared to the “Interceptor®” (same specifications as above) and were also compared to
449 “Olyset Plus®”, a pyrethroid-PBO ITN (10g/kg of PBO and 20g/kg of permethrin incorporated into
450 polyethylene fibres).

451 Finally, Tiono, Ouédraogo ²¹ evaluated the effectiveness of the pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITN “Olyset Duo®”.
452 These were polyethylene nets treated with a combination of 2% w/w permethrin and 1% w/w pyriproxyfen
453 incorporated into polyethylene fibres. These were compared against pyrethroid-only ITNs “Olyset®” (2% w/w
454 permethrin incorporated into polyethylene fibres). Tiono, Ouédraogo ²¹ employed a stepped-wedge design,
455 where five clusters were randomised to the standard “Olyset®” ITNs at baseline and replaced with the “Olyset
456 Duo®” ITNs by the end of the trial (June 2014 to December 2015). **It is worth noting, that the Sumitomo Olyset
457 Duo pyriproxyfen ITN has been withdrawn from the market and is not a WHO pre-qualified net.**

458 **Outcomes**

459 The main outcome measured across all three studies was malaria case incidence. In the Accrombessi, Cook ²⁰
460 trial, malaria case incidence was measured in a cohort of 30 children per cluster (aged 6 months to 10 years)
461 that were randomly selected and actively followed up for 20 months. Similarly, Mosha, Kulkarni ⁴ measured
462 malaria case incidence by actively following one child per household (aged 6-months to 14-years), from 35
463 randomly selected households per cluster, for up to 1-year. A second independent cohort of children from 40
464 randomly selected households per cluster were actively followed for 1-year, 1-year post intervention (e.g. from
465 1-year post to 2-years post). Tiono, Ouédraogo ²¹ however, measured malaria case incidence in approximately
466 2157 (balanced between groups) children aged six months to five years through passive case detection
467 (presentation to health facility with malaria symptoms).

468 The other outcomes measured across all three studies were parasite prevalence and prevalence of anaemia.
469 These outcomes were collected using cross-sectional surveys. Accrombessi, Cook ²⁰ conducted a survey at 6-
470 months and 18-months post implementation of the intervention. This survey included 70 people (of any age)
471 randomly selected in each cluster. Mosha, Kulkarni ⁴ conducted cross-sectional surveys of up to two children
472 per household if they were aged between 6 months and 14 years. These surveys were conducted at 12-months,
473 18-months and 24-months post implementation of the intervention. Mosha, Kulkarni ⁴ also collected data
474 regarding all-cause mortality and malaria mortality during these surveys. Finally, Tiono, Ouédraogo ²¹
475 conducted four cross-sectional surveys of all children in the study area. These surveys were performed in June
476 2014, December 2014, May 2015 and July 2015 (time post intervention ranged from 5-weeks to 9-months). Due
477 to the stepped-wedged nature of this trial, the data from May 2015 represents the survey in which 50% of the
478 clusters randomised had received the intervention and 50% were still using the control ITN. Tiono, Ouédraogo
479 ²¹ also collected all-cause mortality data during these surveys.

480 Malaria infection incidence and incidence of severe disease were outcomes stipulated in the protocol. However,
481 these outcomes could not be synthesised as they were not reported by any of the included studies. Data regarding
482 adverse events was also reported in two studies^{4,21} and contextual information regarding net quality was only
483 reported in one.⁴ Summary characteristics of the included studies has been provided in Table 6. The full details
484 of these studies have been included in the characteristics of included studies tables (S3)

485

486 **Table 6. Summary characteristics of included studies**

Study (location)	Year(s) of study	Dual active ingredient insecticide treated nets		Outcomes reported
		DAI ITN characteristics	Number of clusters, population details and coverage	
Accrombessi 2023 (Benin, Cove, Zagnanado, and Ouinhi Districts)	2020 - 2022	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Interceptor G2 (200 mg/m2 chlorfenapyr and 100 mg/m2 alpha-cypermethrin) 2. Royal Guard (225 mg/m2 pyriproxyfen and 261 mg/m2 alpha-cypermethrin) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clusters = 60 (approximately 200 households per cluster) • Population = Approximately 1200 per cluster (actual numbers not provided) • Overall coverage = one LLIN per every two people (complete details not provided) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Malaria case incidence rate • Parasite Prevalence • Prevalence of anaemia
Mosha 2022 (Tanzania, Misungwi district of Mwanza)	2018 - 2020	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Interceptor G2 (200 mg/m2 chlorfenapyr and 100 mg/m2 alpha-cypermethrin) 2. Royal Guard (225 mg/m2 pyriproxyfen and 261 mg/m2 alpha-cypermethrin) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clusters = 84 (119 households) • Population = 236,496 • Overall coverage = Coverage at baseline measured as 62.2% (Population access) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Parasite prevalence (defined in the study as malaria prevalence) • Malaria case incidence • All-cause mortality • Malaria mortality • Prevalence of anaemia
Tiono 2018 (Burkina Faso, Cascades Region)	2014-2017	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Olyset Duo (2% w/w permethrin and 1% w/w pyriproxyfen) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clusters = 40 (consisting of 1-4 neighboring villages, aka compound). • Population = Population numbers not provided at time of randomization. 6062 households participated • Overall coverage = Coverage at baseline measured as 95% (Population access) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Malaria case incidence rate • Parasite prevalence • All-cause mortality • Prevalence of anaemia

487

488 **Assessment of the risk of bias**

489 **Bias arising from the randomisation process**

490 Randomisation and allocation concealment were achieved through employing an independent statistician in
491 Moshā, Kulkarni⁴ and were judged as having low risk of bias for this domain. Accrombessi, Cook²⁰ stated in
492 their protocol that “Restricted randomisation will be used...” but did not provide the review team with additional
493 information regarding this procedure, or baseline demographics outside of children sex ratios for meta-
494 determination of the randomisation sequence followed. Likewise, Tiono, Ouédraogo²¹ achieved randomisation
495 using “Stata version 10”, however, no further details were provided regarding this process for whether allocation
496 concealment took place. As such, both studies were judged as having ‘some concerns’ for this domain. Moshā,
497 Kulkarni⁴ also provided data for some of their outcomes that had not considered the intra-class correlation
498 coefficient (ICC). This is particularly relevant for any comparison provided in this review against pyrethroid-
499 PBO ITNs. As this raw data has not been appropriately controlled for the ICC, we have decided to consider a
500 high risk of bias for this domain, wherever outcome data was relevant to the pyrethroid-PBO ITNs. (Fig 2).

501 **Fig 2. Risk of Bias Judgements.** Summarised risk of bias judgements using the Cochrane RoB 2.0 tool for
502 cluster randomised controlled trials. Provided for each study and each outcome where relevant.

503 **Bias arising from the timing of identification or recruitment of participants**

504 All studies were regarded as having low risk of bias for this domain. All studies identified clusters before the
505 randomisation process and the baseline demographic data provided by Moshā, Kulkarni⁴ and Tiono, Ouédraogo
506 ²¹ suggest that there were no imbalances between groups which may suggest differential recruitment between
507 groups (this data was not provided for Accrombessi, Cook²⁰).

508 **Bias arising from deviations from intended interventions**

509 All studies attempted to blind participants and staff to the intervention being received. Moshā, Kulkarni⁴ utilised
510 ITNs that were similar in appearance apart from a colour-coded loop. Tiono, Ouédraogo²¹ stated that all ITNs
511 were of similar shape, size and colour. While the methods of blinding for the Accrombessi, Cook²⁰ study have
512 not been provided by the authors, the protocol for this trial states “Study participants will be blinded to the type
513 of nets they have received. All field staff will be blinded to the allocation and analyses will be conducted on
514 blinded data”.¹⁵ As such, the risk of bias for all studies for this domain was low.

515 **Bias arising from missing outcome data**

516 In the Accrombessi, Cook¹⁵ trial, malaria case incidence was measured in a cohort of 30 children per cluster
517 that were randomly selected and followed up for 20 months. Parasite prevalence and prevalence of anaemia
518 were measured following cross-sectional surveys of approximately 70 people (per cluster).

519 Moshā, Kulkarni⁴ measured malaria case incidence by actively following one child, from 35 randomly selected
520 households per cluster, for up to 1-year. A second independent cohort of children from 40 randomly selected
521 households per cluster were actively followed for 1-year, 1-year post intervention (e.g. from 1-year post to 2-
522 years post). The authors also collected parasite prevalence, prevalence of anaemia data and mortality data (all-
523 cause and due to malaria) from cross-sectional surveys of up to two children per household if they were aged
524 between 6 months and 14 years.

525 Finally, Tiono, Ouédraogo²¹ measured malaria case incidence of children aged six months to five years through
526 passive case detection (presentation to health facility with malaria symptoms). A cross-sectional survey of all
527 children in the study area was conducted (when the stepped-wedge design achieved 50:50 split between
528 intervention arms), this survey collected data of parasite prevalence, prevalence of anaemia and mortality.

529 Across all studies and for all outcomes, data was not made available for every participant that belonged to a
530 randomised cluster. However, the process of randomisation (that was evidenced in each study) and randomly
531 selecting participants to provide outcome data, suggests that these results were not biased. Additionally, data
532 was made available from every cluster, for all three studies. As such, all three studies have been judged to have
533 a low risk of bias for this domain, and for every outcome reported.

534 **Bias arising from measurement of the outcome**

535 Measurement of all outcomes examined across every study were deemed to be appropriate (see details regarding
536 outcomes above), and all studies employed an appropriate blinding method (see above) that suggests that
537 blinding of the outcome assessor was likely. Therefore, all studies have been judged to have a low risk of bias
538 for this domain, and for every outcome reported.

539 **Bias arising from selection of the reported results**

540 Accrombessi, Cook²⁰ includes data from 1-year post, 2-year post and overall data for all three outcomes
541 reported above. All this data has been used in the review analyses and has followed a pre-specified analysis plan
542 established in the protocol. Both Mosha, Kulkarni⁴ and Tiono, Ouédraogo²¹ reported multiple analyses of the
543 data for each outcome (time points analysis). However, all the results were reported in the manuscripts
544 transparently and included in this review as appropriate. These analyses were also conducted following the pre-
545 specified analysis plan established in the trial protocols and the risk of bias for all three studies for this domain
546 for each outcome is low.

547 **Overall bias**

548 Overall, the risk of bias was low for all studies across all outcomes (except for outcomes related to pyrethroid-
549 PBO ITNs). Judgments for each included study have been summarised in Figure 2, with support for every
550 judgment have been provided in S3.

551 **Data synthesis and meta-analysis**

552 **Comparison 1 - Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs versus pyrethroid-only ITNs**

553 **Malaria Case Incidence (overall)**

554 Two studies^{4,20} contributed data for this comparison and the below outcomes. There was a 45% reduction in
555 malaria case incidence (overall) in clusters that received chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that
556 received pyrethroid-only ITNs (IRR = 0.55, 95%CI: 0.44 – 0.68, p <0.001, Fig 3). There was no important
557 heterogeneity between these data (I² = 0%, Chi² = 0.01, p = 0.88). Subgroup analyses were conducted for vector
558 species and setting. The ICEMAN credibility assessment identified these subgroups as both having very low
559 credibility. This assessment suggested that effect modification is very unlikely and for the overall estimate to
560 be used. Forest-plots for outcomes that have contributed to the evidence profiles (Tables 1-4) are presented
561 below, all other forest-plots (including all subgroups) are provided in S4. The ICEMAN credibility assessments
562 have been presented in S5.

563 **Fig 3. Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs versus pyrethroid-only ITNs: Malaria Case Incidence (overall)**

564 **Malaria Case Incidence (1-year post intervention)**

565 There was a 53% reduction in malaria case incidence at 1-year post intervention in clusters that received
566 chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-only ITNs (IRR = 0.47, 95%CI: 0.35
567 – 0.63, p <0.001, Fig 4). There was no important heterogeneity between these data (I² = 0%, Chi² = 0.00, p =
568 0.94). Subgroup for vector species and setting using ICEMAN credibility assessment identified these subgroups
569 as both having very low credibility suggesting very unlikely effect modification and for the overall estimate to
570 be used.

571 **Fig 4. Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs versus pyrethroid-only ITNs: Malaria Case Incidence (1-year post)**

572 **Malaria Case Incidence (2-years post intervention)**

573 There was a 33% reduction in malaria case incidence at 2-years post intervention in clusters that received
574 chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-only ITNs (IRR = 0.67, 95%CI: 0.61
575 – 0.75, p <0.001, Fig 5). There may be substantial heterogeneity between these data (I² = 75%, Chi² = 3.99, p
576 = 0.05). Subgroup analyses were conducted for vector species and setting. The ICEMAN credibility assessment
577 identified these subgroups as both having very low credibility. This suggested that effect modification is very
578 unlikely and for the overall estimate to be used.

579 **Fig 5. Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs versus pyrethroid-only ITNs: Malaria Case Incidence (2-year post)**

580 **Parasite prevalence (6-months follow-up)**

581 Accrombessi, Cook ²⁰ reported a 53% reduction in parasite prevalence at 6-months follow-up, in clusters that
582 received chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-only ITNs (OR = 0.47,
583 95% CI: 0.32 – 0.69, p = 0.001, Fig 6).

584 **Fig 6. Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs versus pyrethroid-only ITNs: Parasite prevalence (6-months)**

585 **Parasite prevalence (12-months follow-up)**

586 Mosha, Kulkarni ⁴ reported a 53% reduction in parasite prevalence at 12-months follow-up, in clusters that
587 received chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-only ITNs (OR = 0.47,
588 95% CI: 0.31 – 0.72, p = 0.004, Fig 7).

589 **Fig 7. Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs versus pyrethroid-only ITNs: Parasite prevalence (12-months)**

590 **Parasite prevalence (18-months follow-up)**

591 There was a 37% reduction in parasite prevalence at 18-months follow-up, in clusters that received
592 chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-only ITNs (OR = 0.63, 95% CI: 0.49
593 – 0.80, p = 0.002, Fig 8). There was no important heterogeneity between these data ($I^2 = 0\%$, $\text{Chi}^2 = 0.14$, p =
594 0.71). Subgroup analyses were conducted for vector species and setting. The ICEMAN credibility assessment
595 identified these subgroups as both having very low credibility. This suggested that effect modification is very
596 unlikely and for the overall estimate to be used.

597 **Fig 8. Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs versus pyrethroid-only ITNs: Parasite prevalence (18-months)**

598 **Parasite prevalence (24-months follow-up)**

599 Mosha, Kulkarni ⁴ reported a 55% reduction in parasite prevalence at 24-months follow-up, in clusters that
600 received chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-only ITNs (OR = 0.45,
601 95% CI: 0.30 – 0.68, p = 0.001, Fig 9).

602 **Fig 9. Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs versus pyrethroid-only ITNs: Parasite prevalence (24-months)**

603 **Parasite prevalence (furthest possible follow-up)**

604 There was a 47% reduction in parasite prevalence at the furthest possible follow-up time point, in clusters that
605 received chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-only ITNs (OR = 0.53,
606 95% CI: 0.41 – 0.69, p < 0.001). There was no important heterogeneity between these data ($I^2 = 13\%$, $\text{Chi}^2 =$
607 1.15, p = 0.28). Subgroup analyses were conducted for vector species and setting. The ICEMAN credibility
608 assessment identified these subgroups as both having low credibility. This suggested that effect modification is
609 unlikely and for the overall estimate to be used.

610 **Prevalence of anaemia (6-months follow-up)**

611 Accrombessi, Cook ²⁰ reported a 29% reduction in prevalence of anaemia at 6-months follow-up, in clusters
612 that received chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-only ITNs (OR = 0.71,
613 95% CI: 0.40 – 1.26, p = 0.16).

614 **Prevalence of anaemia (12-months follow-up)**

615 Mosha, Kulkarni ⁴ reported a 45% increase in prevalence of anaemia at 12-months follow-up, in clusters that
616 received chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-only ITNs (OR = 1.55,
617 95% CI: 0.58 – 4.14, p = 0.38).

618 **Prevalence of anaemia (18-months follow-up)**

619 There was a 17% reduction in prevalence of anaemia at 18-months follow-up, in clusters that received
620 chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-only ITNs (OR = 0.83, 95% CI: 0.53
621 – 1.28, p = 0.39). There was no heterogeneity between these data ($I^2 = 0\%$, $\text{Chi}^2 = 0.74$, p = 0.39). Subgroup

622 analyses were conducted for vector species and setting. The ICEMAN credibility assessment identified these
623 subgroups as both having very low credibility. This suggested that effect modification is very unlikely and for
624 the overall estimate to be used.

625 **Prevalence of anaemia (24-months follow-up)**

626 Mosha, Kulkarni ⁴ reported a 6% reduction in prevalence of anaemia at 24-months follow-up, in clusters that
627 received chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-only ITNs (OR = 0.94,
628 95% CI: 0.52 – 1.70, p = 0.84).

629 **Prevalence of anaemia (furthest possible follow-up)**

630 As this data has come from cross-sectional surveys, the survey from each study taken from the longest time
631 post-intervention (where appropriate) was used (Mosha, Kulkarni ⁴ – 24 months, Accrombessi, Cook ²⁰ – 18
632 months). There was a 1% reduction in prevalence of anaemia at the furthest possible follow-up time point, in
633 clusters that received chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-only ITNs (OR
634 = 0.99, 95% CI: 0.62 – 1.58, p = 0.97). There was no important heterogeneity between these data ($I^2 = 0\%$, Chi^2
635 = 0.08, p = 0.78). Subgroup analyses were conducted for vector species and setting. The ICEMAN credibility
636 assessment identified these subgroups as both having very low credibility. This suggested that effect
637 modification is very unlikely and for the overall estimate to be used.

638 **Comparison 2 - Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs versus pyrethroid-PBO ITNs**

639 **Malaria Case Incidence (overall)**

640 Only one study⁴ contributed data for the outcomes under this comparison. Mosha, Kulkarni ⁴ reported a 32%
641 reduction in malaria case incidence (overall), in clusters that received chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs compared
642 to those that received pyrethroid-PBO ITNs (IRR = 0.68, 95% CI: 0.59 – 0.79, p < 0.001, Fig 10).

643 **Fig 10. Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs versus pyrethroid-PBO ITNs: Malaria Case Incidence (overall)**

644 **Malaria Case Incidence (1-year post intervention)**

645 Mosha, Kulkarni ⁴ reported a 2% reduction in malaria case incidence at 1-year post intervention, in clusters that
646 received chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-PBO ITNs (IRR = 0.98,
647 95% CI: 0.71 – 1.36, p = 0.90, Fig 11).

648 **Fig 11. Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs versus pyrethroid-PBO ITNs: Malaria Case Incidence (1-year post)**

650 **Malaria Case Incidence (2-years post intervention)**

651 Mosha, Kulkarni ⁴ reported a 35% reduction in malaria case incidence at 2-years post intervention, in clusters
652 that received chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-PBO ITNs (IRR = 0.65,
653 95% CI: 0.55 – 0.77, p < 0.001, Fig 12).

654 **Fig 12. Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs versus pyrethroid-PBO ITNs: Malaria Case Incidence (2-year post)**

656 **Parasite Prevalence (12-months follow-up)**

657 Mosha, Kulkarni ⁴ reported a 22% reduction in parasite prevalence at 12-months follow-up, in clusters that
658 received chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-PBO ITNs (OR = 0.78,
659 95% CI: 0.62 – 0.97, p = 0.03, Fig 13).

660 **Fig 13. Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs versus pyrethroid-PBO ITNs: Parasite Prevalence (12-months)**

661 **Parasite Prevalence (18-months follow-up)**

662 Mosha, Kulkarni ⁴ reported a 9% reduction in parasite prevalence at 18-months follow-up, in clusters that
663 received chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-PBO ITNs (OR = 0.91,
664 95% CI: 0.77 – 1.04, p = 0.23, Fig 14).

665 **Fig 14. Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs versus pyrethroid-PBO ITNs: Parasite Prevalence (18-months)**

666 **Parasite Prevalence (24-months follow-up)**

667 Mosha, Kulkarni ⁴ reported a 50% reduction in parasite prevalence at 24-months follow-up, in clusters that
668 received chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-PBO ITNs (OR = 0.50,
669 95% CI: 0.42 – 0.60, p <0.001, Fig 15).

670 **Fig 15. Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs versus pyrethroid-PBO ITNs: Parasite Prevalence (24-months)**

671 **Prevalence of anaemia (12-months follow-up)**

672 Mosha, Kulkarni ⁴ reported a 1% reduction in prevalence of anaemia at 12-months follow-up, in clusters that
673 received chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-PBO ITNs (OR = 0.99,
674 95% CI: 0.42 – 2.37, p = 0.03).

675 **Prevalence of anaemia (18-months follow-up)**

676 Mosha, Kulkarni ⁴ reported a 30% increase in prevalence of anaemia at 18-months follow-up, in clusters that
677 received chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-PBO ITNs (OR = 1.30,
678 95% CI: 0.75 – 2.26, p = 0.35).

679 **Prevalence of anaemia (24-months follow-up)**

680 Mosha, Kulkarni ⁴ reported a 4% increase in prevalence of anaemia at 24-months follow-up, in clusters that
681 received chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-PBO ITNs (OR = 1.04,
682 95% CI: 0.60 – 1.80, p = 0.89).

683 **Comparison 3 - Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs versus pyrethroid-only ITNs**

684 **Malaria case incidence (overall)**

685 All three included studies contributed data to this outcome. There was a 10% reduction in malaria case incidence
686 (overall) in clusters that received pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-
687 only ITNs (IRR = 0.90, 95% CI: 0.73 – 1.13, p = 0.37, Fig 16). There was no important heterogeneity between
688 these data ($I^2 = 0\%$, $\text{Chi}^2 = 0.33$, p = 0.85). The data has been separated into subgroups based on active-ingredient
689 composition and manufacturer. However, ICEMAN credibility assessments determined very low credibility,
690 suggesting that that there was very likely no effect modification between these subgroups and the overall effect
691 should be used. Subgroup analysis was also conducted for vector species and setting; however, ICEMAN
692 credibility assessments determined these subgroups to also be very-low. As such, it is very likely that no effect
693 modification was present.

694 **Fig 16. Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs versus pyrethroid-only ITNs: Malaria Case Incidence (overall)**

695 **Malaria case incidence (1-year post intervention)**

696 Only data from Mosha, Kulkarni ⁴ and Accrombessi, Cook ²⁰ have provided data for outcomes regarding time
697 from implementation of the intervention. There was a 34% reduction in malaria case incidence at 1-year post
698 intervention in clusters that received pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-
699 only ITNs (IRR = 0.66, 95% CI: 0.47 – 0.85, p = 0.02, Fig 17). There may be some moderate heterogeneity
700 between these data ($I^2 = 40\%$, $\text{Chi}^2 = 1.67$, p = 0.2). Subgroup analyses were conducted for vector species and
701 setting. The ICEMAN credibility assessment identified these subgroups as both having very low credibility.
702 This suggested that effect modification is very unlikely and for the overall estimate to be used.

703 **Fig 17. Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs versus pyrethroid-only ITNs: Malaria Case Incidence (1-year post)**

704 **Malaria case incidence (2-years post intervention)**

705 There was a 6% reduction in malaria case incidence at 2-years post intervention in clusters that received
706 pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-only ITNs (IRR = 0.94, 95% CI: 0.75
707 – 1.17, p = 0.57, Fig 18). There was no important heterogeneity between these data ($I^2 = 0\%$, $\text{Chi}^2 = 0.86$, p =
708 0.35). Subgroup analyses were conducted for vector species and setting. The ICEMAN credibility assessment

709 identified these subgroups as both having very low credibility. This suggested that effect modification is very
710 unlikely and for the overall estimate to be used.

711 **Fig 18. Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs versus pyrethroid-only ITNs: Malaria Case Incidence (2-year post)**

712 **Parasite prevalence at 6-months follow-up**

713 Accrombessi, Cook ²⁰ reported an 8% reduction in parasite prevalence at 6-months follow-up, in clusters that
714 received pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-only ITNs (OR = 0.92,
715 95% CI: 0.62 – 1.34, p=0.67, Fig 19).

716 **Fig 19. Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs versus pyrethroid-only ITNs: Parasite prevalence (6-months)**

717 **Parasite prevalence (12-months follow-up)**

718 Mosha, Kulkarni ⁴ reported a 31% reduction in parasite prevalence at 12-months follow-up, in clusters that
719 received pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-only ITNs (OR = 0.69,
720 95% CI: 0.46 – 1.04, p =0.08, Fig 20).

721 **Fig 20. Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs versus pyrethroid-only ITNs: Parasite prevalence (12-months)**

722 **Parasite prevalence (18-months follow-up)**

723 There was a 3% reduction in parasite prevalence at 18-months follow-up, in clusters that received pyriproxyfen-
724 pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-only ITNs (OR = 0.97, 95% CI: 0.76 – 1.26, p =
725 0.84, Figure 21). There was no important heterogeneity between these data ($I^2 = 0\%$, $\text{Chi}^2 = 0.0$, $p = 0.97$).
726 Subgroup analyses were conducted for vector species and setting. The ICEMAN credibility assessment
727 identified these subgroups as both having very low credibility. This suggested that effect modification is very
728 unlikely and for the overall estimate to be used.

729 **Fig 21. Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs versus pyrethroid-only ITNs: Parasite prevalence (18-months)**

730 **Parasite prevalence (24-months follow-up)**

731 Mosha, Kulkarni ⁴ reported an 21% reduction in parasite prevalence at 24-months follow-up, in clusters that
732 received pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-only ITNs (OR = 0.79,
733 95% CI: 0.54 – 1.16, p =0.22, Fig 22).

734 **Fig 22. Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs versus pyrethroid-only ITNs: Parasite prevalence (24-months)**

735 **Parasite prevalence (furthest possible follow-up)**

736 All three included studies contributed data to this outcome. The survey from each study taken from the longest
737 time post-intervention (where appropriate) was used (Mosha, Kulkarni ⁴ – 24 months, Accrombessi, Cook ²⁰ –
738 18 months). However, due to the stepped-wedged nature of Tiono, Ouédraogo ²¹, the data from survey conducted
739 in May 2015 has been used. This data represents the longest point in the trial from the implementation of the
740 intervention in which 50% of the clusters randomised had received the intervention and 50% were still using
741 the control ITN. There was a 11% reduction in parasite prevalence at the furthest possible follow-up time point,
742 in clusters that received pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-only ITNs
743 (OR = 0.89, 95% CI: 0.79 – 1.01, p = 0.07). There was no important heterogeneity between these data ($I^2=0\%$,
744 $\text{Chi}^2=0.63$, $p = 0.73$). The data has been separated into subgroups based on active-ingredient composition and
745 manufacturer. However, ICEMAN credibility assessments determined very low credibility, suggesting that that
746 there was very likely no effect modification between these subgroups and the overall effect should be used.
747 Subgroup analysis was also conducted for vector species and setting; however, ICEMAN credibility
748 assessments determined these subgroups to be low and very-low respectively. As such, it is likely to very likely
749 that no effect modification was present.

750 **Prevalence of anaemia at 6-months follow-up**

751 Accrombessi, Cook ²⁰ reported a 24% increase in prevalence of anaemia at 6-months follow-up, in clusters that
752 received pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-only ITNs (OR = 1.24,
753 95%CI: 0.71 – 2.17, p=0.45).

754 **Prevalence of anaemia (12-months follow-up)**

755 Mosha, Kulkarni ⁴ reported a 15% increase in prevalence of anaemia at 12-months follow-up, in clusters that
756 received pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-only ITNs (OR = 1.15,
757 95%CI: 0.40 – 3.31, p=0.80).

758 **Prevalence of anaemia (18-months follow-up)**

759 There was a 13% reduction in prevalence of anaemia at 18-months follow-up, in clusters that received
760 pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-only ITNs (OR = 0.87, 95%CI: 0.56
761 – 1.33, p = 0.51). There was no important heterogeneity between these data ($I^2 = 0\%$, $\text{Chi}^2 = 0.01$, $p = 0.92$).
762 Subgroup analyses were conducted for vector species and setting. The ICEMAN credibility assessment
763 identified these subgroups as both having very low credibility. This suggested that effect modification is very
764 unlikely and for the overall estimate to be used.

765 **Prevalence of anaemia (24-months follow-up)**

766 Mosha, Kulkarni ⁴ reported a 15% increase in prevalence of anaemia at 24-months follow-up, in clusters that
767 received pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-only ITNs (OR = 1.15,
768 95%CI: 0.66 – 2.00, p=0.62).

769 **Prevalence of anaemia (furthest possible follow-up)**

770 There was a 23% reduction in prevalence of anaemia at the furthest possible follow-up time point, in clusters
771 that received pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-only ITNs (OR = 0.77,
772 95%CI: 0.58 – 1.03, p = 0.08). There may have been moderate heterogeneity between these data ($I^2=38\%$,
773 $\text{Chi}^2=3.21$, $p = 0.20$). The data has been separated into subgroups based on active-ingredient composition and
774 manufacturer. However, ICEMAN credibility assessments determined low credibility, suggesting that that there
775 was likely no effect modification between these subgroups and the overall effect should be used. Subgroup
776 analysis was also conducted for vector species and setting; however, ICEMAN credibility assessments
777 determined these subgroups to be very-low. As such, it is very likely that no effect modification was present.

778 **Comparison 4 - Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs versus pyrethroid-PBO ITNs**

779 **Malaria Case Incidence (overall)**

780 Only one study⁴ directly compared any DAI ITN against an ITN that combined a pyrethroid and PBO in the
781 one net. Mosha, Kulkarni ⁴ reported a 25% increase in malaria case incidence (overall) in clusters that received
782 pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-PBO ITNs (IRR = 1.25, 95%CI: 1.10
783 – 1.41, p=0.0005, Fig 23).

784 **Fig 23. Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs versus pyrethroid-PBO ITNs: Malaria Case Incidence (overall)**

785 **Malaria Case Incidence (1-year post intervention)**

786 Mosha, Kulkarni ⁴ reported a 104% increase in malaria case incidence at 1-year post intervention, in clusters
787 that received pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-PBO ITNs (IRR = 2.04,
788 95%CI: 1.55 – 2.68, p <0.001, Fig 24).

789 **Fig 24. Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs versus pyrethroid-PBO ITNs: Malaria Case Incidence (1-year
790 post)**

791 **Malaria Case Incidence (2-years post intervention)**

792 Mosha, Kulkarni ⁴ reported a 10% increase in malaria case incidence at 2-years post intervention, in clusters that
793 received pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-PBO ITNs (IRR = 1.10,
794 95% CI: 0.95 – 1.27, p = 0.19, Fig 25).

795 **Fig 25. Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs versus pyrethroid-PBO ITNs: Malaria Case Incidence (2-year**
796 **post)**

797 **Parasite Prevalence (12-months follow-up)**

798 Mosha, Kulkarni ⁴ reported a 16% increase in parasite prevalence at 12-months follow-up, in clusters that
799 received pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-PBO ITNs (OR = 1.16,
800 95% CI: 0.94 – 1.44, p = 0.16, Fig 26).

801 **Fig 26. Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs versus pyrethroid-PBO ITNs: Parasite Prevalence (12-months)**

802 **Parasite Prevalence (18-months follow-up)**

803 Mosha, Kulkarni ⁴ reported a 34% increase in parasite prevalence at 18-months follow-up, in clusters that
804 received pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-PBO ITNs (OR = 1.34,
805 95% CI: 1.14 – 1.58, p = 0.0005, Fig 27).

806 **Fig 27. Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs versus pyrethroid-PBO ITNs: Parasite Prevalence (18-months)**

807 **Parasite Prevalence (24-months follow-up)**

808 Mosha, Kulkarni ⁴ reported a 12% reduction in parasite prevalence at 24-months follow-up, in clusters that
809 received pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-PBO ITNs (OR = 0.88,
810 95% CI: 0.75 – 1.03, p = 0.11, Fig 28).

811 **Fig 28. Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs versus pyrethroid-PBO ITNs: Parasite Prevalence (24-months)**

812 **Prevalence of anaemia (12-months follow-up)**

813 Mosha, Kulkarni ⁴ reported a 20% reduction in prevalence of anaemia at 12-months follow-up, in clusters that
814 received pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-PBO ITNs (OR = 0.80,
815 95% CI: 0.31 – 2.04, p = 0.63).

816 **Prevalence of anaemia (18-months follow-up)**

817 Mosha, Kulkarni ⁴ reported a 67% increase in prevalence of anaemia at 18-months follow-up, in clusters that
818 received pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-PBO ITNs (OR = 1.67,
819 95% CI: 0.97 – 2.87, p = 0.06).

820 **Prevalence of anaemia (24-months follow-up)**

821 Mosha, Kulkarni ⁴ reported a 38% increase in prevalence of anaemia at 24-months follow-up, in clusters that
822 received pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-PBO ITNs (OR = 1.38,
823 95% CI: 0.82 – 2.32, p = 0.22).

824 **Mortality**

825 Both Mosha, Kulkarni ⁴ and Tiono, Ouédraogo ²¹ reported data regarding mortality outcomes. Mosha, Kulkarni
826 ⁴ reported a total of five deaths among cohort children during the study. While these deaths have been reported
827 per group and year, the reasons (of death) have not been separated by group or year. As reported by the authors
828 three deaths were from drowning, one was due to severe malaria, and one due to pneumonia, all of which were
829 judged to be unrelated to the study interventions. Tiono, Ouédraogo ²¹ reported that there were 19 serious
830 adverse events across all study participants (discussed below), and six of these resulted in deaths (n = 1 [Standard
831 ITN], n = 5 [DAI ITN]). However, the months in which these deaths were recorded was not provided which
832 prevented this data being presented as a forest-plot, as an appropriate denominator could not be determined, due
833 to the stepped-wedge design of the trial.

834 **Adverse Events**

835 Mosha, Kulkarni ⁴ reported that at 3 months post-intervention, adverse events were reported in 90 (44.1%) of
836 those assigned the pyrethroid-only ITN, 80 (38.8%) of those assigned pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs, 17 (8.5%)
837 assigned the chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITN, and 17 (8.5%) of those assigned the pyrethroid-PBO ITN. They also
838 narratively reported that skin irritation was the most reported adverse event, however no adverse event was
839 considered to be serious.

840 Tiono, Ouédraogo ²¹ reported 21 non-serious adverse events in the pyrethroid-only ITN group and one in the
841 pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITN group. The adverse event in this group was a case of bronchitis. The adverse events
842 in the pyrethroid-only ITN group included bronchitis, conjunctivitis, eye pruritus, pelvic pain, pruritus, rhinitis,
843 cough and watering eyes all of which were resolved by study staff. Tiono, Ouédraogo ²¹ also reported 10 serious
844 adverse events in the pyrethroid-only ITN group and 9 in the pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITN group. These
845 included severe malaria with other comorbidities, uncomplicated malaria with vomiting, gastroenteritis with
846 severe dehydration and pneumonia. However, these were not disaggregated between groups.

847 **Contextual Factors**

848 Only Mosha, Kulkarni ⁴ reported data related to contextual factors of the ITNs used during the trial. The authors
849 reported the proportion of ITNs that were torn (defined as hole area ≥ 790 cm²). There were 86 (28%) torn in the
850 pyrethroid-only ITN group, 109 (39%) were torn in the pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITN group, 96 (34%) were torn
851 in the chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITN group, and 81 (43%) were torn in the pyrethroid-PBO group. No study
852 reported any data regarding values or preferences regarding the interventions.

853 **Cost Effectiveness**

854 Cost effectiveness was only reported by Mosha, Kulkarni ⁴ who modelled cost-effectiveness over the 2-year
855 trial period. Malaria incidence estimates for each trial year were combined with probabilities of progression to
856 severe disease and death that were collected from secondary sources. The authors used age-stratified malaria
857 estimates for all countries from the “Global Burden of Disease Study 2019” incidence in people older than 10
858 years was estimated as a function of incidence in children aged 6 months to 10 years, and deaths in people older
859 than 10 years were estimated as a fixed ratio to modelled deaths in children aged 6 months to 10 years. The
860 authors then used Monte Carlo simulation to conduct probabilistic analyses, which reflected combined
861 uncertainty in stochastic parameters. Analyses were re-run, varying one key parameter at a time, to examine the
862 robustness of results to plausible variations in individual parameters. A threshold analysis identified the price
863 of each net at which cost-effectiveness conclusions would change.

864 Mosha, Kulkarni ⁴ stated that chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs were estimated to avert the most DALYs (disability
865 adjusted life years) (mean 152 DALYs averted [SD 72] per 10,000 total population). This was followed by
866 pyrethroid-PBO ITNs (37 DALYs averted [72] per 10,000 population). Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs incurred
867 9 more DALYs [71] per 10,000 population than compared to pyrethroid-only ITNs.

868 Mosha, Kulkarni ⁴ also reported that pyrethroid-only ITNs were the least costly to procure at \$2.07 per net
869 (\$US), this was followed by pyrethroid-PBO ITNs at \$2.98 per net. Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs were the
870 next most expensive at \$3.02 per net, while pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs were the most expensive \$3.68.
871 However, when considering the costs of malaria diagnosis and prevention, and compared to pyrethroid-only
872 ITNs over 2 years the chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs were the least costly (incremental cost \$2894 [SD 1129]
873 per 10 000 population). This was followed by pyrethroid-PBO ITNs (\$4816 [SD 1360]) and pyriproxyfen-
874 pyrethroids ITNs were the most expensive (\$9621 [SD 1327]).

875 Mosha, Kulkarni ⁴ conclude by stating that chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs were the more cost-effective strategy
876 over a 2-year period. Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs would cost an additional \$19 (95%CI from \$105 to \$1) to
877 public providers or \$28 (95%CI from \$11 to \$120) to donors per DALY averted compared to pyrethroid-only
878 ITNs. The pyrethroid-PBO ITNs were less effective and more costly and were estimated to cost an additional

879 \$130 (95%CI from \$12 to -\$59) to public providers and \$136 to donors (95%CI from \$22 to -\$58) per DALY
880 averted.

881 Discussion

882 This is the first systematic review to assess the effectiveness of DAI ITNs against pyrethroid-only or pyrethroid-
883 PBO ITNs. Three, cluster-randomised controlled trials were included in this review. Two studies employed a
884 typical design and were conducted in Benin²⁰ and Tanzania.⁴ One study utilised a stepped-wedge design and
885 was conducted in Burkina Faso.²¹ All studies were conducted in settings with high transmission of *P.*
886 *falciparum*. The interventions investigated included chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs (Interceptor G2) and
887 pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs (Royal Guard and/or Olyset Duo). These interventions have been compared
888 against pyrethroid-only ITNs (Interceptor and/or Olyset) or pyrethroid-PBO ITNs (Olyset Plus). All studies
889 utilised similar modes of intervention implementation and achieved a high coverage of the ITNs at baseline.

890 When collapsing the data across time points, the evidence suggests that clusters that receive a chlorfenapyr-
891 pyrethroid ITN (Fig 3) will likely result in a reduction of malaria case incidence compared to clusters that
892 receive a pyrethroid-only ITN. This finding was associated with high certainty of the evidence (Table 1).
893 Compared to the control group, the reduction in malaria case incidence appears to be greater for the clusters
894 receiving the chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITN (Fig 3) than the reduction observed for clusters receiving the
895 pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITN (when collapsing across time points) (Fig 16). However, this difference as with
896 all results discussed in this section, needs to be contextualised by a guideline panel.

897 At 1-year post intervention, the evidence suggests that clusters that receive either a chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITN
898 (Fig 4) or pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITN (Fig 17) will result in a reduction of malaria case incidence compared
899 to clusters that receive pyrethroid-only ITNs. Both findings were associated with high certainty of the evidence
900 (Table 1 and 3). At 2-years post-intervention the evidence suggests that, compared to clusters receiving
901 pyrethroid-only ITNs, clusters that receive chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs (Fig 5) will also result in a reduction
902 of malaria case incidence (Table 1). However, this was not observed in clusters that received pyriproxyfen-
903 pyrethroid ITNs (Fig 18, Table 3). These findings were associated with High and Low certainty evidence
904 respectively. For both time points it appears that the reduction in malaria case incidence is greater for the clusters
905 receiving the DAI ITN containing chlorfenapyr and pyrethroid, than the reduction observed for clusters that
906 received the DAI ITN containing pyriproxyfen and pyrethroid (both compared to clusters receiving pyrethroid-
907 only ITNs).

908 Parasite prevalence at 6-months follow-up was only reported by Accrombessi, Cook²⁰ for both formulations of
909 DAI ITNs. The authors have reported that both clusters receiving both formulations resulted in a reduction in
910 parasite prevalence. However, chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs appear to offer a greater reduction (Fig 6, Table 1)
911 with higher certainty of the evidence, compared to pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs (Fig 19, Table 3) with
912 moderate certainty of the evidence. Parasite prevalence at 12-months and 24-months follow-up was only
913 reported by Mosha, Kulkarni⁴ for both formulations of DAI ITNs. For the data at both the 12-month time point
914 and 24-month time point, the authors have reported that clusters receiving chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs (Fig 7
915 and 9) resulted in a reduction of parasite prevalence, compared to clusters receiving the pyrethroid-only ITN.
916 These findings were associated with high and moderate certainty evidence respectively (Table 1). For clusters
917 that received pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs (Fig 20 and 22), there was no difference in parasite prevalence
918 compared to control clusters at these time points. These findings were both associated with moderate certainty
919 in the evidence (Table 3).

920 For parasite prevalence at 18-months, the evidence suggests that clusters that receive either formulation of DAI
921 ITN will result in a reduction of parasite prevalence (Fig 8 and 21). However, chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs
922 appear to offer a greater reduction in parasite prevalence, associated with higher certainty of the evidence Table
923 1), compared to the reduction offered by pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs (Table 3), which was only associated
924 with low evidence.

925 Only one study⁴ compared both formulations of DAI ITN against pyrethroid-PBO ITNs. Compared to
926 pyrethroid-PBO ITNs, the authors have reported that clusters that received chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs were
927 associated with reduced malaria case incidence when collapsed across time points (Fig 10), for 1-year post
928 intervention (Fig 11), and for 2-years post intervention (Fig 12). These findings were associated with moderate,
929 very low, and moderate certainty of the evidence, respectively (Table 2). Likewise, for the outcome of parasite
930 prevalence a reduction was observed for the clusters that received chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs at 12-months
931 (Fig 13), 18-months (Fig 14) and 24-months (Fig 15) post follow-up. These findings were associated with low,
932 low, and moderate certainty in the evidence, respectively (Table 2).

933 For clusters that received pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs, the authors have reported that compared to clusters
934 that received pyrethroid-PBO ITNs, there was an increase in malaria case incidence when collapsed across time
935 points (Fig 23), at 1-year post intervention (Fig 24), and for 2-years post intervention (Fig 25). These findings
936 were associated with moderate, moderate, and low certainty of the evidence (Table 4). This was also consistent
937 for the outcome of parasite prevalence, where increases were observed for parasite prevalence in the clusters
938 that received pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs at 12-months (Fig 26), 18-months (Fig 27), and 24-months (Fig 28)
939 post follow-up compared to those that received pyrethroid-PBO ITNs. These findings were associated with low,
940 moderate, and low certainty of the evidence, respectively (Table 4).

941 There are some limitations to these findings. Only three studies were identified that met the inclusion criteria of
942 this review, however all these studies are recent (within the last 5 years) have compared similar interventions,
943 have implemented the interventions uniformly achieving high coverage, and have reported similar results. The
944 major differences between these studies included the manufacturer of the ITNs compared, the main vectors of
945 interest and their setting. However, upon conducting subgroup analyses (S4) and ICEMAN credibility
946 assessments (S5) none of these factors were deemed to be effect modifiers. It is also important to note, that the
947 analyses conducted were ill-suited to detect sub-group differences, due to so few studies being included, and
948 each study having been conducted in different settings and with different dominant vector species. As effect
949 modification is viably plausible, we emphasise that while we did not detect effect modification from any of the
950 investigated subgroups, uncertainty remains, and effect modification may still be present. Future research is
951 needed on these types of nets to investigate this concern.

952 All studies were cluster randomised controlled trials and therefore, the overall certainty in the body of evidence
953 started as high. The impact of DAI ITNs has been evaluated in lower-level evidence, however this has not
954 contributed to the evidence synthesised as part of this review. Publication bias was unable to be assessed during
955 this review as only three studies were included. However, the comprehensive search strategy and reaching out
956 to authors directly ameliorated some concerns of publication bias in this review.

957 Conclusion

958 We have high certainty evidence that chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs are more effective than pyrethroid-only
959 ITNs in reducing malaria case incidence. This benefit also extends to parasite prevalence for which we have
960 moderate-high certainty evidence. However, only chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs demonstrated a reduction in
961 these outcomes when compared to pyrethroid-PBO ITNs.

962 Despite most of this evidence being high-moderate certainty, only three studies were included in this review.
963 These studies were conducted in high transmission settings, and additional studies conducted in other
964 transmission settings would further strengthen the evidence base in favour of chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid DAI
965 ITNs. Future trials should also explore these interventions for longer than 2-years post implementation of the
966 intervention to provide more robust data as to their long-term effectiveness.

967 **Contributors**

968 THB was involved in the development of the protocol, the screening of the studies identified through the search,
969 assessment of risk of bias and extraction of data of included studies, synthesis of extracted data, development
970 of GRADE evidence profiles and drafting the final manuscript.

971 JCS was involved in the screening of the studies identified through the search, assessment of risk of bias and
972 extraction of data of included studies.

973 SH was involved in the screening of the studies identified through the search, assessment of risk of bias and
974 extraction of data of included studies.

975 CP was involved in the development of the search strategy and performing the search across databases.

976 AK was involved in the development of the protocol and drafting the final manuscript.

977 ZM was involved in the development of the protocol, development of GRADE evidence profiles and drafting
978 of the final manuscript.

979 All authors had full access to the data in the study and had the final decision to submit this work for publication.

980 **Declaration of interests**

981 We declare no competing interests.

982 **Data sharing**

983 Related documents including the supporting information referenced in this manuscript will be made freely
984 available as supplementary material to this manuscript.

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990 members of the Guideline Development Group for this project.

991 **Deviations from protocol**

- 992 1. No need to adjust standard errors for failing to account for clustering as all studies had done so
993 appropriately. Where raw data has been used, risk of bias implications have been taken into consideration.
994
- 995 2. The following subgroups were specified in the protocol but were not conducted for the stated reasons
996 a. Level of transmission; (High: incidence of about 450 cases/1000 persons/year or Plasmodium
997 falciparum (Pf) / Plasmodium vivax (Pv) prevalence of $\geq 35\%$; Moderate: incidence of 250-450 per
998 1000 persons per year and Pf/Pv prevalence of 10-35%; Low: incidence of 100-250 per 1000 persons
999 per year and Pf/Pv prevalence of 1-10%; Very low: incidence of < 100 per 1000 persons per year and
1000 Pf/Pv prevalence $< 1\%$.) (the level of transmission will be categorized according to the schema found
1001 in the *Framework for malaria elimination*)²⁴ ; seasonality of transmission (Not conducted as all
1002 studies were from high transmission settings)
1003 b. Species of parasite (Not conducted as all studies explored *P. falciparum*)
1004 c. Coverage of intervention applied and level of net coverage per person or household (Not conducted
1005 as all studies had a high intervention coverage)

- 1006 d. Durability of net and insecticides used (No study had provided sufficient data regarding net
1007 durability. As the assessment of durability was not the focus of this review this subgroup has been
1008 omitted).
- 1009 e. Characteristics of insecticides used, e.g., target sites, modes of action, and duration required to
1010 produce such effect(s). (The subgrouping parameters of this pre-specified group were identical to
1011 the “insecticide class” subgroup that has been presented in the review. As such, these two subgroups
1012 have been combined and reported together in the review.
- 1013 f. Population demographics e.g., sex/age/SES/ethnicity etc. All included studies provided population
1014 demographics for the study cohorts. These demographics were similar enough to not warrant
1015 subgrouping).
- 1016 g. Human behaviour (e.g. sleeping behaviour) (Two studies had provided this information, however
1017 one study had not. After contacting the authors for this information, it was not received and the two
1018 remaining studies were not different enough to warrant subgrouping).
- 1019 h. Coverage of other background interventions. (All included studies confirmed that no other
1020 interventions were being carried out in the trial region during the study period. As such, no
1021 subgrouping necessary).
- 1022
- 1023 3. Sensitivity analyses was originally planned conducted to analyse the following (below). However, as all
1024 the included studies were at low risk of bias, and had appropriately controlled for clustering it was
1025 unnecessary.
- 1026 a. The impact of bias by excluding studies that are at a high risk of bias.
- 1027 b. Where we have inflated standard errors for trials where cluster designs have not been considered,
1028 we will analyse trials as if the individual was the unit of randomisation.
- 1029
- 1030 4. The following outcomes were not included in the GRADE evidence profiles due to a lack of available
1031 data from the included studies:
- 1032 a. Malaria infection incidence
- 1033 b. Incidence of severe disease
- 1034 c. All-cause mortality
- 1035 d. Malaria mortality
- 1036

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1095

1096 **Supporting information**

1097 **S1. Complete search strategies**

1098 **S2. Studies extracted at full text**

1099 **S3. Characteristics of included studies**

1100 **S4. Additional conducted analyses**

1101 **S5. ICEMAN credibility assessments**

1102

1103